

Saint Achillios Basilica, Larissa

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The basilica dedicated to Saint Achillios in the city of Larissa, Greece, is situated on the so-called hill of the fortress, between the ancient theatre and the Ottoman marketplace. The church, preserved today in a ruinous state, was discovered in July 1978, in the course of the works for the enhancement of the city's centre. In the following years, the excavation that has taken place permitted to identify the edifice as the basilica dedicated to Saint Achillios († 330), which also sheltered his tomb. According to Saint Achillios's Vita written in the middle of the 9th century, he was born in Cappadocia. He has held the metropolitan seat of Larissa for 35 years, while he was one of the bishops who have participated in the First Council of Nicaea of 325. The Saint has sensed his death requested the preparation of the sarcophagus in which he was going to be buried. The Vita mentions that his relics were forgotten and lost and that they were rediscovered through divine revelation 300 years later. His cult developed from the 9th century onwards, while it gained widespread popularity in the 10th century. The connection of the excavated basilica with Saint Achillios was based on the discovery of a well's cover with the inscription "ΑΧΙΛΛΙΟΥ ΑΡΧΙΕΠΙΣΚΟΠΟΥ + ΚΑΙ ΤΟΥΤΟ ΤΟ ΕΡΓΟΝ", as well as the stamp ΑΧΙΛΛΙΟΥ on the bricks, used for the construction of the monument. The three-aisled, timber-roofed basilica measures 29.10 m by 17.80 m and is composed of an apse, a narthex and an exonarthex, which has replaced the pre-existent gallery. The significant dispersion of fragments of the monument, mainly during the Ottoman period, has led to the loss of evidence regarding its superstructure. The mosaic floor has also suffered important damages, as only some fragments in the narthex depicting birds and plants, bordered by geometric decoration, have survived. The basilica was adorned with sculptural decoration, fragments of which were discovered during the excavations. The erection of the building can be estimated to the middle of the 6th century, while it was most probably renovated in the 9th century, following the revival of Saint Achillios's cult. The basilica has undergone significant modifications throughout its history: the initial floor level was raised; a semi-circular apse was attached to the north aisle, associated with the vaulted tomb decorated with foliate crosses, identified as Saint Achillios's tomb; two more simply decorated tombs (in the central aisle and in the outer part of the narthex) were constructed in the monument; and, lateral buttresses were added for reinforcing the walls. Around the basilica were found many tombs, indicating the funerary character of the building from the middle Byzantine period onwards, a use that continued even after it collapsed, probably in the end of the 15th century.

Date Range: 550 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Larissa

Region tags: Greece, Thessaly, Larissa

The city of Larissa is the capital of Thessaly region in Greece

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gialouri, A., and A. Plastara. Βασιλική Αγίου Αχιλλίου Λάρισσας. Larissa: Hellenic Ministry of Culture and Sports, 7th Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities, 2013.
- Source 2: Sofianos, D. “Ο Άγιος Αχιλλεῖος Λαρίσης.” *Μεσαιωνικά Και Νέα Ελληνικά* 3 (1990).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://youtu.be/tZe-6vFRb9c>
- Source 1 Description: Short documentary on the Basilica of Saint Achillios in Larissa
- Source 2 URL: http://larisa.culture.gr/images/odngoi/agios_axillios.pdf
- Source 2 Description: Short guide of the Basilica of Saint Achillios in Larissa by the Ephorate of Antiquities of Larissa
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.larissa-culturestories.gr/vr/basiliki/basiliki.html>
- Source 3 Description: Virtual tour of the Basilica of Saint Achillios in Larissa

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1978-1999

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: Excavation of the Basilica of Saint Achillios of Larissa

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: The monument was built on the hill of the fortress, in the centre of the city of Larissa

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The monument was built in the centre of the city of Larissa

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The monument was built in the centre of the city of Larissa

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– Yes

The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: The basilica is preserved in a ruinous state, for it was discovered and excavated at the end of the 20th century

↳ One single feature
– Other [specify]: The basilica has an array of features

↳ A group of structures:
– No

↳ A group of features:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

Notes: The three-aisled, timber-roofed basilica is composed of an apse, a narthex and an exonarthex, which has replaced the pre-existent gallery

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: The basilica dedicated to Saint Achillios sheltered also his tomb and so it was also a place of pilgrimage

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

Notes: The basilica has undergone significant modifications: the initial floor level was raised; a semi-circular apse was attached to the north aisle, associated with the vaulted tomb decorated with foliate crosses, identified as Saint Achillios's tomb; two more simply decorated tombs (in the central aisle and in the outer part of the narthex) were

constructed in the monument; and, lateral buttresses were added for reinforcing the walls.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

Notes: The basilica must have collapsed in the end of the 15th century, and it may be connected to the erection of the nearby bedestan

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: It is connected with the erection of the bedestan, but the reasons of the basilica's destruction are not really known

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Human-caused accident

– Other [specify]: The reasons of the basilica's destruction are not really known

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The basilica was not rebuilt. Yet, it has undergone significant modifications throughout its history: the initial floor level was raised; a semi-circular apse was attached to the north aisle, associated with the vaulted tomb decorated with foliate crosses, identified as Saint Achillios's tomb; two more simply decorated tombs (in the central aisle and in the outer part of the narthex) were constructed in the monument; and, lateral buttresses were added for reinforcing the walls.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– I don't know

Notes: This is possible, but there is no evidence that could support this hypothesis.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– I don't know

Notes: This is possible, but there is no evidence that could support this hypothesis.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Notes: The basilica was built in honour of Saint Achillios

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions

and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

- Other [specify]: The monument is in a ruinous state, so it is not possible to know about all the materials used

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

- I don't know

Decoration

Is decoration present:

- Yes

↳ Are there mosaics present:

- Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

- Other [specify]: The mosaics display plant and animal decoration bordered by geometric motifs

- Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

- Yes

↳ On the outside:

- No

↳ On the inside:

- Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

- No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

- Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The mosaic decoration and the architectural ornamentation of the basilica include birds

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: The mosaic decoration and the architectural ornamentation of the basilica include floral motifs.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

Notes: On a well's cover was discovered the inscription "ΑΧΙΛΛΙΟΥ ΑΡΧΙΕΠΙΣΚΟΠΟΥ + ΚΑΙ ΤΟΥΤΟ ΤΟ ΕΡΓΟΝ". The bricks used for the construction of the monument were stamped ΑΧΙΛΛΙΟΥ

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: On a well's cover was discovered the inscription "ΑΧΙΛΛΙΟΥ ΑΡΧΙΕΠΙΣΚΟΠΟΥ + ΚΑΙ ΤΟΥΤΟ ΤΟ ΕΡΓΟΝ". The bricks used for the construction of the monument were stamped ΑΧΙΛΛΙΟΥ

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The reliefs of the architectural elements are decorative and not narrative

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

– Secco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The tombs are decorated with crosses

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The mosaics display plant and animal decoration bordered by geometric motifs

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Crosses

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There is no narrative iconography in the monument

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: The monument is not a burial. However, it contains the tomb of Saint Achillios and two more tombs. Around the basilica were found many tombs, indicating the funerary character of the building

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: The relics of Saint Achillios are not preserved in the building anymore. They were moved to the basilica of Saint Achillios in Prespes (Macedonia)

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Around the basilica were found many tombs, indicating the funerary character of the building

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The basilica was not initially planned and built for hosting the relics of Saint Achillios

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: The basilica is not a functioning monument anymore

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: Those are undertaken by the 7th Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities of Ministry of Culture and Sports of Greece

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: Permanent staff of the 7th Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities of Ministry of Culture and Sports of Greece

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The basilica is not a functioning religious monument anymore

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: This is functioning mostly as an archaeological site

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Notes: The monument is not functioning currently. However, ecclesiastical authorities are involved in the decision-making regarding its conservation and dissemination

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The 7th Ephorate of byzantine antiquities of the Ministry of Culture and Sports of Greece

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: The basilica is mentioned by the Vita of Saint Achillios, written in the middle of the 9th century

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– No

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Saint Achillios Basilica, Larissa, Gialouri, A., and A. Plastara. Βασιλική Αγίου Αχιλλίου Λάρισσας. Larissa: Hellenic Ministry of Culture and Sports, 7th Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities, 2013.

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Λάρισα, 26-28 Απριλίου 1985. Larissa, 1985.

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